

**Final Year Project – Report On:
"SUPERMASSIVE BLACK HOLES: FORMATION AND
EFFECT ON THE GALAXIES"**

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ACKNOWLEDGMENT

I would like to acknowledge that the writing of this document is inspired by the "Ph.D.'s Thesis of Mr. Daniel S. Eastwood, by the name of "The growth of massive seed black holes and their impact on their host galaxies", for The University of Edinburgh.

I would like to express my sincere gratitude to several individuals and organizations for supporting me throughout our research. I wish to express our sincere gratitude to my supervisor, Mr. Azad Hussain and Co-supervisor Dr. Shakeel Mehmood for their enthusiasm, patience, insightful comments, helpful information, practical advice and unceasing ideas that have helped me tremendously at all times in our research and writing of this report. Their immense knowledge, profound experience and professional expertise in physics has enabled us to complete this research successfully. Without their support and guidance, this project would not have been possible. Thanks for all your encouragement.

ABSTRACT

I investigated the formation of the Supermassive black holes (SMBHs) in high redshift galaxies, with the goal of providing insights to which galaxies do or do not host SMBHs. I adopted a novel approach to forming seed black holes in galaxy halos in cosmological Halo Model.

I analytically modelled the growth of gravitational instabilities in an isolated proto-galaxy disc as it progresses into a fully-formed galaxy in the presence of a massive seed black hole formed directly through isothermal collapse of pristine gas. The model shows for the first time how the gravitational effects of a seed black hole lead to an increase in the stability of the disc and an increase in the star formation timescale in the region of the disc close to the black hole and then compared the factors of model with age of universe.

I also investigated how the viscosity driven inflow of gas effects the SMBHs and this study concluded that isolated black hole seeds alone cannot grow into the desired size , thus mergers interaction are considered between galaxies. The result of this model was observed through simulation of a merger galaxy.

TABLE OF ABBREVIATIONS

ACRONYM	FULL FORM
SMBH	SUPERMASSIVE BLACK HOLE
DCBH	DIRECT COLLAPSE BLACK HOLE
UV	ULTRAVIOLET
LW	LYMAN WERNER
DM	DARK MATTER
CDM	COLD DARK MATTER
SMS	SUPERMASSIVE STAR

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CHAPTER 01

INTRODUCTION:

PHYSICS OF BLACK HOLE:

There is an Old Persian tale that once, a swarm of butterflies held a summer school to solve the great mystery of the flame. All of them discussed different models, but none could describe the puzzle convincingly. Then one of the Butterflies volunteered to get a practical experience of flame. He flew off to the closest castle, passed in front of a window, and saw the light of a candle. He went back, told what he had seen. But the older butterfly who was the chair of the conference said that this is not any new information to them.

Then, a second butterfly flew off to the castle, crossed the window, and touched the flame with his wings. He hardly came back and told his experience; the wise butterfly said "*Your explanation is still not satisfactory*". Then a third butterfly went to the castle, hit the candle, and burned himself into the flame. The wise butterfly, who had observed the action, said to the others: "*Well, our friend has learned everything about the flame. But only he can know, and that's all*".

As for morals, this story can easily be transposed from butterflies to researchers confronted with the mystery of black holes. Some astronomers, equipped with powerful instruments such as large orbiting telescopes, make very distant and indirect observations on black holes; as the first butterfly, they acknowledge the real existence of black holes but they gain very little information on their real nature.

Next, theoretical physicists' study black holes using higher mathematical tools such as general relativity, quantum mechanics, and higher mathematics; same as the second butterfly, they get a little bit more information, but not so sufficient. The equivalent of the third butterfly would be an astronaut plunging directly into a black hole, but eventually, only he himself would know that information.

BLACK HOLE (BHs):

A black hole is an object so dense that space and time around it are inescapably modified, warped into an infinite sink. Nothing, not even light, can move fast enough to escape a black hole's gravitational pull once it passes a certain boundary, known as the **event horizon**. Thus, a black hole is like a cosmic vacuum cleaner with infinite capacity, gobbling up everything in its path, and letting nothing out.

***"It is a region of space-time in which the gravitational potential, GM/R , exceeds the square of the speed of light."* (contributors, 2020)**

The idea of a black hole dates back to more than 235 years. In the 18th century, a scholar, John Michell gave the first idea on black holes. In one of his famous talks at the Royal Society in London, he concluded that light would not leave the surface of a very massive star if the gravitation was sufficiently large and if such large objects exist in nature, then light from them can never reach us. After a decade, the French mathematician, physicist, and astronomer Pierre-

Simon de Laplace used the idea of John Michell and called such objects as '*Dark Stars*'. Their theory also gave rise to the concept of *Escape Velocity*,

"Minimum speed that an object at a given distance from a gravitating body must have so that it will continue to move away from the body instead of orbiting about it."

$$v_c = \sqrt{\frac{2GM}{R}} \quad (1.1)$$

But this thought experiment was based on Newton's theory of light that's why it did not meet a large response.

In 1915, Albert Einstein gave the theory of General relativity which later served as the theoretical basis for the black holes. In 1916, a German astronomer and a military officer, Karl Schwarzschild crafted a solution of Einstein's theory of gravity that concluded

"Enough matter packed into as small-enough space would have such powerful gravitational field that nothing could escape from it, including light."

This proved a very important finding for black hole

As they gave rise to the first parameter of the black hole, *Schwarzschild radius*

Putting $v_c = c$ (speed of light) in eq (1.1)

$$v_c = c = \sqrt{\frac{GM}{R}}$$

Squaring both sides,

$$c^2 = \frac{GM}{R}$$

Re-arranging

$$R = \frac{GM}{c^2}$$

where this R is called *Schwarzschild radius*, r_{sch} .

$$r_{sch} = \frac{GM}{c^2} \quad (1.2)$$

$G = 4.302 \times 10^{-3} \text{ pc } M^{-1} (\text{km/s})^2$ is the gravitational constant.

M = the mass of the object within a radius, R .

The [Sun](#) has a Schwarzschild radius of approximately 3.0 km (1.9 mi), whereas [Earth's](#) is only about 9 mm (0.35 in) and the [Moon's](#) is about 0.1 mm (0.0039 in). Thus, we can also define a black hole in terms of Schwarzschild radius.

"Any object whose radius is smaller than its Schwarzschild radius is called a black hole."

In 1963, Maarten Schmidt discovers that 3c273 a star-like point of light known as a Quasar, one of the most powerful objects in the universe. His finding further leads to the fact that every quasar is powered by a **supermassive black hole** present at the center of a galaxy.

Figure 1-1 Quasar 3C 273 taken by Hubble Space Telescope. Its light has taken some 2.5 billion years to reach us. Despite this great distance, it is still one of the closest quasars to our home.

In 1971, astronomers identified the first possible stellar mass' black hole, **Cygnus X-1** fig (1-2) by combining X-ray, radio, and optical observation from a telescope in space and ground.

Figure 1-2 Chandra X-ray Observatory image of Cygnus X-1.

In 1974, Stephen Hawking concluded that black holes also emit radiations called *Hawking Radiations*, which will eventually cause them to disappear. In the same year, astronomers also discovered a radio source at the center of the Milky Way emitting radiation. It was titled Sagittarius A*(Fig 1-3) with an asterisk that stands for "exciting", well, in the "excited atoms" perspective.

In 2000, astronomers found another important fact that every galaxy has a supermassive black hole present in its heart and the evolution of galaxies is related to those supermassive black holes. This raised the question that what came first, the Galaxy or the Blackhole?

And answer to this question was that "*Black holes came first*", and then steadily galaxy grew around this black hole.

Figure 1-3 Chandra Image of Sgr A, showing how it can be resolved into finer detail, including a small point source called Sagittarius A.*

Credit: [NASA Chandra X-Ray Observatory](#) and [Penn State University](#)

TYPES OF BLACK HOLES:

Black holes can be divided into four main categories:

1) Stellar black holes :

The smaller ones, called stellar-mass black holes, have a mass up to 100 times larger than that of our sun. They're formed when a massive star consumes all its nuclear fuel and its core collapses. We've observed several of these objects as close as 3000 light-years away, and there could be up to 100 million small black holes just in the Milky Way galaxy. Their mass ranges between 0.1- 100 solar masses.

2) Supermassive Black hole :

These enormous black holes are millions or even billions of times as massive as the sun but are about the same size in diameter. Such black holes are thought to lie at the

center of pretty much every galaxy, including the Milky Way. Their mass ranges between $10^5 - 10^{10}$ solar masses.

3) Intermediate Black holes :

Recent research has revealed the possibility that midsize, or intermediate, black holes (IMBHs) could exist. Such bodies could form when stars in a cluster collide in a chain reaction. Several of these IMBHs forming in the same region could then eventually fall together in the center of a galaxy and create a supermassive black hole. In 2014, astronomers found what appeared to be an intermediate-mass black hole in the arm of a spiral galaxy. Their mass ranges from $100 - 10^5$ solar masses.

4) Mini- black holes :

The tiniest members of the black hole family are, so far, theoretical. These small vortices of darkness may have swirled to life soon after the universe formed with the big bang, some 13.7 billion years ago, and then quickly evaporated. Their mass ranges from 0-0.1 solar masses.

Figure 1-4 Size of black holes

SUPERMASSIVE BLACK HOLES:

Super-massive black holes (SMBHs), such as Sagittarius A* at the center of our Milky-Way, have been observed with masses $M_{\bullet} \sim 10^6 - 10^{10} M_{\odot}$ at the center of galaxies throughout the local universe (Kormendy & Richstone 1995; Magorrian et al. 1998). About 1-2% of nearby galaxies have bright central nuclei with spectra that look similar to quasars. These "active galactic nuclei" (AGN) appear to be scaled-down versions of quasars, less luminous because a black hole is less massive or because a massive black hole is being fed slowly. The higher percentage of galaxies has faint AGN.

Most massive galaxies are thought to play host to a central massive black hole, and the masses of these black holes correlate with the properties of their host galaxies (Magorrian et al. 1998; Merloni et al. 2003; Merritt 2006; Kormendy & Bender 2009; Kormendy & Ho 2013; Heckman

& Best 2014; Reines & Volonteri 2015; Thomas et al. 2016). Researches are going on to look at the higher redshift to understand the correlations between galaxy and SMBHs.

The most distant quasar fuelled by SMBH ever discovered was at $z \sim 7$, but recently (Banados et al.) (2018) detected quasar ULAS *J134208.10+092838.61* (hereafter J1342+0928) at $z = 7.54$ with a black hole mass of $M_{\bullet} = 8 \times 10 M_{\odot}$. But the age of the universe at this redshift is only 690 million years old, this raised the question that how can such incredibly heavy supermassive black holes form within a few hundred million years after the Big Bang when this is basically in the first blink of the cosmic baby's eye? The biggest problem is that no known method can be used to squash the fantastic amount of normal matter into a sufficiently small volume to make a supermassive black hole within a hundred million years.

The growth of compact objects such as black holes occurs through either the accretion of surrounding material or mergers. The process of accretion heats the material falling onto the black hole. The in-falling material can then radiate, efficiently converting the potential energy gained to radiation. (Eastwood2019). The growth of a black hole is limited by balancing the resulting radiation pressure against the infall of material under gravity at equilibrium. This is provided by the *Eddington limit*,

" *The maximum luminosity a body (such as a star) can achieve when there is a balance between the force of radiation acting outward and the gravitational force acting inward.*"

Consider force which photons exert on surrounding gas when a fraction of them are absorbed:

The sources of radiation are:

- Luminosity L
- Spherically symmetric emission
- Energy flux, at a distance $\frac{L}{4\pi r^2}$
- Each photon has momentum $p = \frac{E}{c}$
- Momentum flux = $\frac{\text{Energy flux at a distance}}{\text{speed of light}} = \frac{L}{4\pi cr^2}$

If the source is surrounded by gas with opacity σ_{τ} , then in traveling distance ds the fraction of radiation absorbed is:

$$\frac{dI}{I} = -\sigma_{\tau} \times \rho ds$$

Where $\rho ds = \text{column density of the gas}$.

σ_{τ} , can be defined as the fraction radiation absorbed by a unit column of gas. Force exerted by the radiation on that gas is then given by

$$f_{rad} = \frac{\sigma_{\tau} L_{bh}}{4\pi cr^2} \quad (\text{outward force})$$

Force due to gravity on that gas (unit mass):

Figure 1-5

$$f_{grav} = \frac{GM_{bh}m_p}{r^2} \quad (\text{inward, toward mass})$$

Radiation pressure balances gravity when:

$$f_{rad} = f_{grav}$$

$$\frac{\sigma_\tau L_{bh}}{4\pi cr^2} = \frac{GM_{bh}m_p}{r^2}$$

$$L_{edd,bh} = \frac{GM_{bh}4\pi cm_p}{\sigma_\tau} \quad (1.3)$$

If L is larger than this value the pressure due to radiation exceeds the gravitational force at all radii, and gas will be blown away.

Critical luminosity is called the Eddington limit. Depends upon:

- The mass of a star
- The opacity of gas surrounding the source

Gas flowing toward black holes produces radiation as the gravitational potential energy is released. Mathematically it can be written as

$$L_{accretion} = \eta \dot{M} c^2$$

Where,

L_{acc} = Accretion luminosity

η = Radiative efficiency of the accretion process = the fraction of the rest mass energy of the gas that is radiated

\dot{M} = Gas inflow rate (the accretion rate): units g s^{-1}

For a black hole accreting matter through a disk, **the radiative efficiency = 0.1**

Setting the accretion luminosity equal to the Eddington limit gives us the **maximum** rate at which a black hole can accrete gas:

$$L_{edd} = L_{acc}$$

$$\frac{GM_{bh}4\pi c}{\sigma_\tau} = \eta \dot{M} c^2$$

$$\dot{M} = \frac{4\pi G m_p}{\eta \sigma_\tau c} M_{bh} \quad (1.4)$$

Figure 1-6

This critical accretion rate is proportional to the mass of the accreting object, which implies that the mass of an object that is growing at the maximal (Eddington) accretion grows exponentially on a timescale known as the *Salpeter time* τ_{sal} . So from eq 1.4,

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{M}_{Edd} &= \frac{M_{bh}}{\tau_{sal}} & (1.5) \\ \tau_{sal} &= \frac{\eta\sigma_{\tau}c}{4\pi Gm_p} \sim 45\eta_{0.1}10^6 \text{ years} \end{aligned}$$

A black hole with some initial mass $M_{bh,i}$ at t_i growing continuously at the Eddington the limit will reach the following mass at the time, t : (Eastwood2019)

$$M_{bh,i}(t) = M_{bh,i} \exp\left[\frac{t - t_i}{\tau_{sal}}\right] \quad (1.6)$$

The growth rate of a black hole is then limited to grow on an e-folding time with the Salpeter time-scale. (Eastwood 2019)

Super Massive Black Hole (SMBHs): Formation

The massive growth of a black hole in such a small time is still a mystery that remains at large. We studied three different theoretical mechanisms for the creation of these supermassive black holes

- Population (III) remnants
- Star clusters
- Direct collapse Blackhole (DCBHs)

Population (III) Remnants:

"The first generation of stars, are known as Population III (PopIII) stars."

Research had shown that the first and the smallest as system (of primordial gas) capable of making stars, called *mini-haloes*, should have appeared between 100 million and 250 million years after the big bang. These mostly consisted of the

- *Dark matter*, the putative elementary particles that are believed to make up 90 percent of the universe's mass

Figure 1-7 The first star-forming systems—small protogalaxies—consisted mostly of the elementary particles known dark matter (shown in red). Ordinary matter—mainly hydrogen gas (blue)—was initially mixed with the dark matter.

- **Metallicity**, only hydrogen, and helium were present in significant amounts. That's why the stars formed by these primordial clouds were called Population (III) stars, as they have no metals at all.
- **Virial temperature** is less than 10^4 K.

These low-mass haloes are expected to collapse around $z \sim 20 - 30$. (Eastwood 2019). The dominant mini-halo cooling species *is molecular hydrogen*. The resulting cooling of the gas leads to fragmentation during cloud collapse and stars can form. When compared to star formation in higher metallicity gas, the relative inefficiency of H_2 cooling results in significantly higher initial stellar masses.

This cooling of gas separates dark matter from normal matter. The cooled hydrogen is settled into a disk-like shaped rotating configuration, but as dark matter does not radiate or lose energy, they would remain scattered. This star-forming system will resemble a primordial galaxy with the disk made up of ordinary matter and halo consisted of dark matter. The denser parts of gas will contract and some will collapse and become stars.

The minimum mass that a clump of gas must have to collapse under its gravity is called **The Jeans mass**.

$$J_{mass} \propto T_{gas}$$

$$J_{mass} \propto \frac{1}{\sqrt{P_g}}$$

Where T_{gas} = temperature of gas

P_g = Pressure of gas

As the temperature of the first collapsing gas was 30 times higher than the current, their jeans mass would have been 1000 times larger. This estimated mass depends upon the chemistry of hydrogen molecules. In 2001 a researcher, **Volker Bromm** used numerical simulations to study the accretion onto a primordial protostar. The calculations show that a Population III star grows to roughly 50 solar masses within the first 10,000 years after the initial core forms. That estimates that during its full lifetime it grows to 100 to 200 solar masses which will make them more massive and luminous than the sun.

Stars that are 250 times more massive than the sun end their lives forming black holes. Hence, the first stars formed the first seed black holes which would have merged to form a supermassive black hole.

Figure1- 8 comparisons between the sun and First Stars

However, there are several issues with this theory of the formation of supermassive black holes:

- IMF, *the initial mass function* is an empirical function that describes the initial distribution of masses for a population of stars, is very uncertain. (*Klessen, 2018*). If several low mass PopIII stars form within a single halo, fewer high mass stars are expected to form, while on the other hand, lone PopIII stars forming in mini-haloes could also result in lower final stellar masses (*Volonteri, 2010*).
- Another research showed that the number density of PopIII remnants black holes is too low for mergers to play any role in their growth. (*Johnson et al. 2013*) which means that accretion would be the only process available for the growth of black holes to reach the mass of a supermassive black hole but *Renaissance* simulation by (*Smith et al, 2018*) showed that even the fastest black holes only grew to 10% of their mass, which concludes that by this rate of growth the black holes could hardly reach the mass of intermediate black hole. But they cannot reach a mass of supermassive black hole $\dot{M} \sim 10$ solar masses. at $z \sim 6$.
- It is, therefore, more likely that the seeds of SMBHs are more massive than PopIII remnants, commanding a more significant gravitational influence over their host haloes and avoiding the need for such intensive gas accretion (*Eastwood, 2019*).

All these results concluded PopIII remnant is not a suitable candidate for the formation of the supermassive black hole.

Figure 1-9 Stages from 1st stars to the supermassive black hole

Star Clusters:

Pop (II) stars formed when mini holes that now contain more metallicity than their ancestors merged to form a massive halo. The enrichment of metallicity results in the cooling of gas and fragmentation rapidly than Pop (III) and thus initiates an era of star formation and produced *the first star clusters*.

The contraction of their cores results in numerous stellar collisions that result in the formation of very massive stars (VMS) which could, later on, gave birth to a massive black hole. Simulations have shown how runaway collisions of stars can lead to significant mass loss which is made worse at high metallicity (*Glebbeek et al. 2009*) which limits the seed black holes.

At low, but not zero, metallicity the situation is more favorable to the formation of massive seed black holes as mass losses through stellar winds and collisions are reduced. (*Eastwood, 2019*). Furthermore, stars at low metallicity with masses ≥ 40 solar masses are predicted to form black hole remnants without losing significant mass through supernovae (*Heger et al. 2003*).

Star clusters are usually formed in the pre-galactic disc. Star formation is mostly prevented in the outer part of the disc as high intensities UV photon dissociate molecular hydrogen to atomic hydrogen due to which infall gas provoke star formation in the central region of the disc. The resulting compact stellar cluster then undergoes core collapse fast timescales, forming a VMS and ultimately a seed black hole of mass $M_{bh} \sim 10^3$ solar masses at $z \sim 10 - 20$ (*Devecchi & Volonteri 2009*).

Direct Collapse Black Hole:

Another formation scenario is the direct collapse of a protogalactic gas cloud, which yields black hole seed masses of $10^4 - 10^6$ solar masses (*Rees 1984; Loeb & Rasio 1994; Bromm & Loeb 2003a; Koushiappas et al. 2004; Begelman et al. 2006; Lodato & Natarajan 2006; Volonteri 2010; Shang et al. 2010; Schleicher et al. 2010*)

Figure 1-10 The visible/near-IR photos from Hubble show a massive star, about 25 times the mass of the Sun, that has winked out of existence with no supernova, or any other explanation. Direct Collapse is the only available option.

This is the most suitable candidate for the creation of SMBHs. This mechanism is fully discussed in chapter 2. This mechanism does not require any kind of stars or supernova, they are purely based on the concept of general relativistic instability. But these kinds of black holes are very rare to find in-universe as there is less probability of finding all suitable conditions in the same gas cloud. Cosmological models suggest that DCBH could only be found as ~ 1 per cubic Giga-parsec at $z \sim 15$. In 2016, a team led by Harvard University astrophysicist **Fabio Pacucci** identified the first two candidate direct collapse black holes, using data from the *Hubble Space Telescope* and the *Chandra X-ray Observatory*.

CHAPTER 2

MECHANISM: DIRECT COLLAPSE BLACK HOLE (DCBHS)

PROCEDURE OF DCBH

We explain this mechanism by which supermassive black holes (SMBHs) can be born directly in the heart of protogalaxies, excluding ‘seed’ black holes left over from early star formation. Self-gravitating gas in dark matter haloes can drop angular momentum rapidly through runaway, overall dynamical instabilities, the so-called ‘bars within bars’ mechanism. This proceeds to the brisk build-up of a dense, self-gravitating core supported by gas pressure – encircled by a radiation pressure-dominated Disk – which gently shrinks and is compressed moreover by subsequent in fall, leading to the formation and quick growth of a central black hole called *Direct Collapse Black hole*.

Direct collapse black hole (DCBH) are thought to form from the fresh early gas halo with low spin, with the Virial temperature above $T \gtrsim 10^4$ K and exposed to strong Lyman-Werner (LW, photons (with energy between 10.2 eV and 13.6 eV) or near-infrared (NIR) radiation (with energy above 0.76 eV) for dissociation of H_2 molecules. This criterion of formation of DCBH is highly specific and has been explained and satisfied with the high redshift universe. Furthermore, fresh (primordial) gas in haloes with Virial temperatures of $T_{\text{vir}} \sim 10^4$ K is expected to collapse at $z \sim 10$ to form compact gas discs. The disc material can then quickly get accreted towards the center of the halo and form a seed black hole, possibly via a temporary super-massive star (SMS) phase.

Some key issues are discussed in the next subheadings that may jeopardize the formation of a black hole through Direct collapse.

FACTORS AFFECTING DCBHS FORMATION

The formation of black holes through a direct collapse mechanism is not ideal. In fact, some factors affect their formation in multiple ways. Addressing these factors has been a need to understand the DCBHs phenomenon. Up till now according to the research, the formation of

direct collapse black holes is affected by the fragmentation in gas clouds and redistribution of angular momentum.

Fragmentation in gas clouds

The term fragmentation means to get divided into multiple pieces or parts, so, in DCBHs, fragmentation refers to splitting up of gas clouds into fragments and restricting the formation of black holes; the more the clouds fragment, the less gas is available for the formation of black holes. Cloud collapse ability usually depends on the gas temperature, isothermal nature of clouds, pressure, and atomic and molecular hydrogen. In general, a collapsing cloud will not fragment at an instant when the jeans mass approaches to a minimum rather it fragments when the cloud collapse has almost stopped.

i. Gas Temperature:

The first factor that influences the fragmentation of clouds is gas temperature. To avoid fragmentation, the gas temperature of $T_{gas} = 10^4$ K or lower than virial temperature has to be maintained. The reason for gas to be lower than virial temperature is that the gas condenses isothermally to collapse upon itself under self-gravity, resulting in the formation of DCBHs, otherwise smaller clumps form, and chances for DCBHs get restricted focusing Star formation process

The degree to which gas will fragment is determined by the Ratio of T_{vir} to T_{gas} ($\frac{T_{vir}}{T_{gas}}$) and the Spin parameter of halo (λ). If the $\frac{T_{vir}}{T_{gas}} \cong 2.9$ then the clouds tend to fragment in stars while if the $\frac{T_{vir}}{T_{gas}} \sim 1$, then the disc fragments are avoided and accretion occurs at the center resulting in the formation of DCBHs.

In the gas temperature, *Virial temperature* plays a vital role. It is defined as “*The mean temperature at which the gravitationally bound system would satisfy the Virial theorem*”, where the Virial theorem says that potential energy must be equal to kinetic energy for astronomical bodies within a factor of two. it establishes the following relation;

$$\langle k \rangle = -\frac{1}{2} \langle U \rangle \quad \dots \quad 2.1$$

Where these brackets tell us the long term averages of both. From the above equation, we can estimate the velocity of Halo, estimated sizes, and temperature of the halo based on the Virial theorem.

ii. Pressure:

The pressure term includes the relationship between gravitational potential and outward pressure. When the gravitational potential equals the outwards pressure the system is in equilibrium and no cloud collapse occurs. Only a slight change in the pressure and potential is required for the clouds to collapse. When the pressure is lowered slightly, gas collapses isothermally forming the central object. Whereas, if the pressure is lowered drastically, no isothermal gas collapse occurs and fragments are produced due to proto galaxy disc.

iii. Atomic and Molecular Hydrogen:

For the DCBH formation, gas fragmentation and star formation must be prevented. DCBH requires the isothermal collapse of gas clouds at $T \sim 10^4$ K and it is possible if the primordial gas contains H_2 as a dominant gas coolant and prevents the formation of molecular hydrogen during the collapse. To understand this process scientists have been performing experiments on arbitrary atomic-cooling halos and artificially turning off the molecular cooling. These artificial model methods at least tell us about the dissociation of H_2 which is necessary to learn to understand the DCBH mechanism.

H_2 cooling is an important scenario and it can be done via two processes; by exposing the in-falling gas to strong Lyman-Werner (LW) ($E = 10.2 - 13.6$ eV) UV flux coming from nearby sources or photo-detachment of H^- , which catalyzes the formation of H_2 by infrared (IR) radiation with energy, $E > 0.76$ eV. This can be expressed with the following equations:

Furthermore, there is no dust nor metal in the early universe, the primordial cloud loses the internal energy via H_2 cooling. For the evolution of molecular hydrogen fraction, we discuss two main channels; the three-body hydrogen reactions and H-channels. These reactions are the important channels for the formation and destruction of molecules. Molecular hydrogen is produced in a high-density region through "*three-body hydrogen reaction ($H_2 + H \rightarrow 3H$)*" and in a low-density region through "H⁻ channel". Following reactions are given for H- channel;

1. H⁻ channel:

2. H⁺² channel:

In channels 1 and 2, H⁻ and H⁺² act as the catalyzers for the final product H₂, respectively. H₂ is mainly formed through H⁻ channel at $z \lesssim 100$. The reason why we consider the two-step formation process is because, since H₂ has no electric dipole moment, the transition rate from two unbound hydrogen to the bound pair of hydrogen is negligibly small. The quadruple transition allows the direct formation of H₂ while the formation rate appears to be much smaller than those by the two-step processes. We can estimate the H₂ abundance by integrating the formation rate in the following manner:

$$f_{H_2} = \int^t dt k_{form} n_x(t) \sim k_{form} n_x t_{rec} = \frac{k_{form}}{\alpha} \sim 3.5 \times 10^{-4} \left(\frac{T}{1000 K} \right)^{1.52} \equiv f_{H_2,s},$$

.... 2.8

Where K_{form} is the reaction rate of channel 1's equation 2 and T is the cloud temperature. The abundance of H₂ indicates the direct increase in the dissociation of H₂.

Angular Momentum:

For the successful formation of DCBH the gas must collapse isothermally without fragmenting and efficiently transfer the angular momentum. The redistribution of angular momentum is extremely important because if the angular momentum is not efficiently transferred during the collapse, the gas will have problems to get accreted inwards. The gas disc will grow gradually with the incoming baryons from outside the halos; this will lead the disc to become unstable and further towards fragmentation which ultimately favors star formation instead of forming a seed black hole via direct collapse. This can be achieved if gas loses angular momentum at early stages of collapse with angular speed $v_\phi(t)$ obey,

$$v_\phi(t) \gtrsim \frac{c r_{sch}}{r(t)} \quad \dots 2.9$$

Where c is the speed of light in a vacuum, r_{sch} is the Schwarzschild radius corresponding to the mass of the collapsing cloud, and $r(t)$ is the radius of the cloud.

Moreover, the dimensionless spin parameter λ is also a factor that determines the degree of fragmentation in a gas cloud. it is expressed as;

$$\lambda = \frac{J|E|^{\frac{1}{2}}}{GM^{\frac{5}{2}}} \quad \dots 2.10$$

In the above expression, J is a measure of the total angular momentum of a halo and, E and M are the energy and mass of the halo, respectively. Numerical simulations have found the distribution in the spin parameter of halo with moment (spin) $\lambda = 0.05$. It tells that for typical $T_{vir} \gtrsim 10^4$ at $z \sim 10$, in isothermal collapse, the angular momentum will lead to the formation of a disk for the further inflow of the material towards the center will require the transfer for the angular momentum of the disc outward by gravitational instability. It is therefore thought that's why DCBH formation is more likely to occur in lower spin haloes.

CHAPTER 03

STAR FORMATION

Stars are the main driver of galaxy evolution. Stars are not only the fundamental building blocks of galaxies but also of the universe. If you want to understand how galaxies evolve, since galaxies consist of stars, so it is really important to understand how these stars evolve. If you want to understand where did the heavy elements in the universe came from, then you need to understand how stars are formed because those heavy elements are made in stars. Moreover, an active field of astronomy is how the planetary system is formed. You cannot understand how planets are formed unless you understand how stars are formed.

So basically, star formation is the crux of anything happening in the universe. Here, we have highlighted some of the conditions that are necessary for the formation of stars.

JEANS CRITERION

Star formation can only take place when the gas is unstable to gravitational collapse. The gas properties will change throughout the protogalactic disk. Some regions of the protogalactic disk can be more unstable than others. To form stars, the gas density has to be above a certain threshold mass, which is called jeans mass given as

$$M_J = \left(\frac{5k_B T_{gas}}{G\mu m_H} \right)^{\frac{3}{2}} \left(\frac{3}{4\pi\rho} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \propto T_{gas}^{\frac{3}{2}} \mu^{-\frac{3}{2}} \rho^{-\frac{1}{2}}$$

Derivation

Starting from the virial theorem (It describes that a system stays in equilibrium if the total energy of system E and the gravitational potential energy U are related as

$$E = U/2$$

But the total energy is

$$E = K + U$$

From virial theorem

$$\frac{U}{2} = K + U$$

$$U = 2K + 2U$$

$$2K + U = 0$$

For a star to form, its kinetic energy must be greater than potential energy (energy stored in an object)

$$2K > |U| \quad (\text{a})$$

In a gas cloud, kinetic energy is due to the motion of atoms that make up the cloud, so if there are N total number of atoms then KE is

$$K = \frac{3}{2}kT(N)$$

$$K = \frac{3}{2}NkT \quad (\text{i})$$

Where N can be written in terms of mass as

$$N = \frac{M}{\mu m_H}$$

Putting in (i)

$$K = \frac{m}{2} \left(\frac{M}{\mu m_H} \right) kT$$

$$K = \frac{3MkT}{2\mu m_H} \quad (\text{ii})$$

$\mu = \text{mean molecular mass}$

Potential energy for a spherical body of uniform density is

$$U = -\frac{GMm}{r}$$

$$dU = -\frac{GMdm}{r} \quad (\text{iii})$$

$$dm = 4\pi\rho r^2 dr$$

$$M = \frac{4}{3}\pi\rho r^3$$

Putting the above two equations in (iii)

$$dU = -G \frac{(4/3\pi\rho r^3)(4\pi r^2\rho)}{r} dr$$

$$dU = -\frac{16}{3}G\pi^2 r^4 \rho^2 dr$$

$$U = \int_0^R \left(-\frac{16}{3}G\pi^2 r^4 \rho^2 dr \right)$$

$$U = -\frac{16}{15}G\pi^2 \rho^2 R^5 \quad (\text{iv})$$

$$U = \frac{16}{15} G \pi^2 \rho^2 \left(\frac{3M}{4\pi R^3} \right)^2$$

$$U = -\frac{3}{5} \frac{GM^2}{R}$$

Assuming,

$$V = \frac{4}{3} \pi R^3$$

$$V = \frac{M}{\rho}$$

Comparing above two equations

$$\frac{m}{\rho} = \frac{4}{3} \pi R^3$$

$$R = \left(\frac{3M}{4\pi\rho} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} \quad (v)$$

Putting values (iii), (iv) and (v) in (a)

$$2 \frac{3MkT}{2\mu m_H} > \frac{3}{5} \frac{GM^2}{\left(\frac{3M}{4\pi\rho} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}}}$$

$$M_J > \left(\frac{5k_B T_{gas}}{G\mu m_H} \right)^{\frac{3}{2}} \left(\frac{3}{4\pi\rho} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

$$M_J \propto T_{gas}^{\frac{3}{2}} \mu^{-\frac{3}{2}} \rho^{-\frac{1}{2}}$$

TOOMRE STABILITY PARAMETER

Another method for star formation to occur is to make any gas unstable against gravitational collapse. Star formation can take place if the protogalactic disk is unstable. This can be justified by the Toomre stability parameter which is given as

$$Q_{Toomre} = \frac{\kappa\sigma}{\pi G \Sigma_d}$$

Where κ is the epicyclic frequency, σ is velocity dispersion

This stability parameter describes the condition in which the protogalactic disk is stable against gravitational collapse. In that case, star formation is suppressed. If $Q_{Toomre} > 1$, then the disk is stable and no star formation will occur. However, if $Q_{Toomre} < 1$, then the protogalactic disk is unstable. The local surface gravity will dominate and stars will form.

STAR FORMATION LAW

Moving forward; describing star formation rate. It is the total mass of stars formed per unit area per unit time. Star formation rate is important in understanding the evolution of galaxies. It was thought that the star formation rate is directly related to the gas surface density. This was presented by Kennicutt and Schmidt.

$$\Sigma_{SFR} \propto \Sigma_g^n$$
$$\Sigma_{SFR} = A \left(\frac{\Sigma_{gas}}{1M.pc^{-2}} \right)^n M.yr^{-1}kpc^{-2}$$

$$n = 1.4 \pm 0.15$$

$$A = (2.5 \pm 0.7) \times 10^{-4}$$

SFR surface density is measured in $M.pc^{-2}$, solar masses per year per square parsec. However, Σ_{gas} is measured in gpc^{-2} , grams per square parsec it describes how efficiently a gas can turn into a star.

CHAPTER 04:

NON-EVOLVING NON-STAR FORMING CASE:

In this case, we have considered that the gaseous disk is not evolving with time (it is not developing).

The mass of Halo is kept constant $M_{200} = 0$

No stars are forming which means stellar mass is zero $M_* = 0$

To investigate the effect of a seed black hole on a galaxy forming in its host halo it is necessary to investigate the inner region of the proto-galactic disc. For this reason, we take the radial dependencies of the system's properties into account. The surface brightness of a galaxy is set by the density of stars inside it. It is an intrinsic property of the galaxy.

For spiral galaxies, the surface brightness declines with distance from the center of the galaxy. This is one simple law for the radial distribution of surface brightness of the disks, called exponential surface brightness law.

$$\Sigma_g(R) = \Sigma_{g,0} \exp(-R/R_d)$$

The surface brightness at the center is increasing and outside it is falling exponentially. Here R_d and $\Sigma_{g,0}$ are the disc scale length and central surface density and are related to the disc mass through **an Invalid source specified**.

$$R_d = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \left(\frac{j_d}{m_d} \right) \lambda r_{200}$$

Since we are working with the disc. And we know that the local stability of the disc against gravitational collapse is parametrized by the Toomre stability parameter. The Toomre parameter is given by

$$Q_{Toomre} = \frac{\kappa \sigma}{\pi G \Sigma_d}$$

$\sigma = \text{velocity dispersion}$

$\kappa = \text{epicyclic frequency}$

$$\kappa^2 = \frac{2\Omega}{r} \frac{dr^2}{dr}$$

If $Q_{Toomre} > 1$, the disc is stable to gravitational instabilities; $Q_{Toomre} < 1$, the disc is unstable and $Q_{Toomre} \sim 1$, the disc is partially stable.

Similar to the Toomre parameter, another parameter that defines that is important for star formation is a tidal parameter

$$Q_{tidal} = Q_{Toomre} \frac{v}{\kappa}$$

Which is related to the tidal forces from the supermassive black hole.

Q_{tidal} behaves similarly to Q_{Toomre} because both have direct relation as can be seen from the above equation.

STABILITY PARAMETER

At a smaller radius, Q_T increases as the mass of the black hole increases. Q_T is directly proportional to κ , therefore κ increases. Because κ provides rotational support against gravitational instability. Therefore, an increase in κ with the increase in black hole mass will stabilize the innermost region of the disk because the gravitational effects are stronger there. As the black hole mass increases, the disk becomes more stable and the regions of star

$$Q_{\text{Toomre}} = \frac{\kappa \sigma}{\pi G \Sigma_d}$$

$$\kappa^2 = \frac{2\Omega}{r} \frac{dr^2 \Omega}{dr}$$

We have considered the disc of constant mass/ surface density. After reaching minima, the radius increases as a result the disc surface density decreases because mass is constant. From the Toomre relation, know that Q_T has an inverse relation with disc surface density. As a result, the stability parameter, Q_T increases.

Here we have considered the non-star forming case. Because when we do mathematical modelling, we always start from the simplest case and then use its results for complex modeling.

This is a non-star-forming case. But we know that when the $Q_T < 1$, the disc becomes unstable and star formation takes place.

The graph is an experimental result.

Graph 4-2

As the mass of the black hole increases, the tidal forces have a strong effect on the disk when the radius is less. As the radius increases, the effect of tidal forces decreases to a minimum value.

$$Q_{tidal} = Q_{Toomre} \frac{\nu}{\kappa}$$

We have considered the disc of constant mass/ surface density. After reaching minima, the radius increases as a result the disc surface density decreases because mass is constant. From tidal relation, we know that Q_t has a direct relation with Q_T , which has an inverse relation with disc surface density. As a result, the stability parameter, Q_t increases.

CHAPTER 05

EVOLVING HALO MODEL

HALO

“A halo is an extended, roughly spherical component of a galaxy which extends beyond the main, visible component.”

A Galactic halo can be divided into three categories:

1. Stellar Halo:

It usually refers to the part of the halo that contains the stars. It is a nearly spherical population of field stars and globular clusters. They are like the fossils of the galaxies. It contains the oldest and the poorest metallicity stars. Because of the presence of old stars, we study it to get information about the environment in which the galaxy grew in its initial phases. Studies of the Milky Way galaxy have found that approximately 0.1-1% of its total stellar mass is contained within the stellar halo and that it extends to over 100-kilo parsecs from the galactic center. (*Cooper, A. P.; Cole, S.; Frenk, C. S, 2010*)

2. Galactic Corona:

It is a distribution of gas extending far away to the ends of the galaxy. Galactic coronas are massive, invisible gas and dust regions that surround the visible bulk of the galaxy, creating a spheroidal shape. Coronas are so hot that their X-ray emission could be identified far beyond the optical radius of the galaxy. Because they're so wispy, these are extremely difficult to detect.

Galactic coronas are an example of revealing indicators that astronomers aim to help them decide how galaxies shape. Despite the progress made in recent decades, the mechanism of galaxy formation remains an open issue in astronomy. Various theories have been proposed, but since galaxies come in all shapes and sizes—including elliptical, circular, and irregular—no single explanation has so far been able to clarify the origins of all the galaxies we see in the Universe.

3. Dark matter halo:

The dark matter halo is a speculated distribution of dark matter that spreads well beyond its visible components in the galaxy. The mass of the dark matter halo is much greater than the mass of the other constituents of the galaxy. Its presence is proposed to account for the gravitational potential that governs the dynamics of bodies within galaxies. The origin of

dark matter halos is an important area of current cosmology researches in particular its relationship to galactic creation and evolution.

DCBH HOSTING HALOES:

The formation of a seed black hole through a direct collapse is expected to take place in haloes within regions of high-intensity local LW radiation (**Agarwal et al. 2012**). Recent studies have shown a local source of H₂ dissociating radiation from nearby quasars or PopII or PopIII stars is required (**Agarwal et al. 2016b**) to provide the critical LW intensity. Hence, the characteristics of the protogalaxies model will represent a bigger galaxy in its initial phase.

The LW radiation field is assumed to be sufficient to entirely dissociate molecular hydrogen in the proto-galaxy and the gas temperature is set to $T_g = 8000$ K. Due to this assumed proximity there is a strong likelihood of a DCBH hosting halo to undergo a merger in its evolution (**Agarwal et al. 2014**). Seed black holes in dark hosting haloes can grow in two ways:

- Isolated, Growing Halo
- Merging of a Halo containing a Collapse black hole, with another proto-galaxy containing stars.

Process of Merging of Two Halos:

- Consider a pair of haloes at a very small separation that crossed the atomic threshold at the nearly same time.
- The first halo in the pair to cross the cooling process will form stars.
- These haloes will merge, with the second halo orbiting the first one.
- While stars are made in 1st halo, the second halo will also complete its cooling process.
- Because it is exposed to the nearly formed galaxy, it is exposed to LW- radiation and forms a DCBH.

Figure 5-1 Merging of Halo as Formation of DCBH

Our Milky Way is also an example of a merging halo system. It is derived from *Gaia-Enceladus* 10 billion years ago.

Figure 5-2 Merging of Milky Way Proto-galaxy and Gaia-Enceladus.

As mentioned above, the cooling in DCBH hosting haloes must be limited to occur via atomic hydrogen (Agarwal et al. 2012).

This limits the metallicity, the virial temperature, and therefore the halo mass. Therefore all designed haloes have $T_{\text{vir}} \sim 10^4$ and the gas consists of atomic hydrogen and helium. For simplicity, the cooling timescale is believed to be very short and the cooling happens at the dynamic time of the halo, implying that the halo-accreted gas enters the proto-galaxy at the dynamic time of the halo. (Dekel et al. 2009; Khochfar & Silk 2011).

GROWTH OF HALOES:

The system of the halo is composed of four main things:

- A gaseous disc
- A stellar Disc
- A black hole
- A dark matter halo.

We have modeled the time evolution of this system. The model follows the evolution of a growing galactic disc in an isolated host halo after the creation of a DCBH seed at some initial redshift, z_i , to some later redshift z_f . SMBHs have been observed $z_f \sim 6:0$ (Fan et al. 2006; Mortlock et al. 2011). The seed formation redshift for the fiducial model is $z_i \sim 10$ (Agarwal et al. 2012) through a range of seed formation redshifts are possible (e.g. Begelman et al. 2006)

The mass of the whole system M_{tot} , is divided into two parts:

- DM halo
- Baryons, that are the basic unit of galaxy disc and Blackhole

For the required conditions for the model, we can calculate initial mass $M_{\text{tot},i}$ by considering the mass of hydrogen cooling halo at initial redshift. We introduce another term known as the baryon fraction, *it is the amount of hydrogen present in-universe the today either in the form of stars galaxies, or hot gas around the galaxies.* we use the universal fiducial value of $f_b = 0.17$.

To calculate the growth of the system through cosmological accretion, we used the equation (Dekel et al. (2013))

$$M_{\text{tot}}(z) = M_{\text{tot},i} e^{-\alpha(z-z_i)}$$

Here $\alpha = \text{halo growth parameter}$. The fiducial values are given in the table:

Parameter	Definition	Fiducial (Range)
M_{seed}	Black hole seed mass (M_{bh})	10^6 (10^{6-4})
f_{Edd}	Eddington fraction	0.25 (0.0 – 1.0)
α	Halo growth parameter	0.806 (0.806, 0.586)
z_i	Seed formation redshift	10.0 (20.0 – 10.0)
z_{infall}	In-fall redshift	0.0 (10.0; 8.5, 7.0, 0.0)

Table 1 Table for fiducial values of parameters

The major assumption of the model is that all baryons are utilized in the mass of the disc and central black hole and any accreted baryon will directly to the disc to conserve mass. So we can calculate the mass of disc at any time t ,

$$\text{Mass of disc} = \text{Total baryonic mass} - \text{Mass of a black hole}$$

Simultaneously, for the growth of the black hole as discussed in chapter 1 we use Eddington fraction f_{edd} ,

$$M_{bh}(t) = M_{seed} \left(f_{edd} \frac{t - t_i}{t_{sal}} \right)$$

$t_{sal} = \text{Salpeter time scale}$

As a black hole can only accrete gas, which means with a high Eddington fraction, the accretion rate can exceed the baryonic growth of halo. (*Eastwood, 2019*).

The previous models were growing with the pristine gas means with no metals (for single halo). But for the case of merging haloes with the protogalaxies, it would increase the metallicity of the halo, which would increase the parameters such that cooling rates, decreasing gas temperature, and inducing disc instabilities leading to higher star formation rate thus higher stellar masses than previously predicted by the model.

CHAPTER 06:

GALAXIES: INTERACTIONS AND MERGERS:

For much of 20th century astronomers believed that galaxies are like *'Island universe'* existing in isolation, without having any contact between them. Later observational studies found that galaxies are shaped by processes that are dependent upon the matter present inside the galaxies. As more galaxies are coming to light, astronomers used computer simulations to observe deeply into these galaxies. The observation from these simulations opened a new door to the evolution of galaxies and predict a new method for their interaction known as *mergers*.

Figure 6-1 Simulation of two galaxies merging

The galaxy mergers take hundreds of millions of years. Thus, collisions are best depicted via simulation on computer, which helps the astronomers to study the different parameters, if the collision is slow, the merging galaxies may unite to form a single galaxy.

Galaxy mergers and interactions form a key part of our understanding of how galaxies form and evolve over time. In cold dark matter cosmology, dark matter halos merge under hierarchical growth (*e.g. Conselice 2014; Somerville & Davé 2015*).

This interaction results in the disruption of the galaxies that lie at the centre of the dark matter halos. Tidal forces act to pull and distort the galaxies, moving stars within the galaxies from the disk to the spheroid component (*e.g. Toomre & Toomre 1972; Somerville & Davé 2015, and references therein*)

Figure 6-2 Merging timescale of two galaxies

GALAXY MERGER- NGC 6240:

NGC 6240 is a remnant of a galaxy collision between three spiral galaxies. This merged body has three supermassive black holes at its center, and around them a vast quantity of gas which is forming new stars at an immense rate. The three black holes are spiralling towards each other and ultimately may become one even larger black hole.

NGC 6240 is located in the *Ophiuchus* (which means Serpent-Bearer) constellation, a mere 98 Mpc or around 3.2×10^8 light-years from the Milky Way.

As, with respect to the size of the observable Universe, NGC 6240 is nearby to our own galaxy, it provides an opportunity to easily witness a galaxy collision. Even so, collisions are surprisingly common, although it is difficult to get an exact estimate; NASA's Hubble Space Telescope found results implying between 5% to 25% of galaxies were merging. It is expected that the Milky Way will eventually collide with the Andromeda galaxy - our closest spiral galaxy, in about 4 billions years.

Figure 6-3 This is an image of the galaxy merger NGC 6240. The shape of this combined-galaxy is clearly very irregular. NGC 6240 is the product of two Milky Way sized spiral galaxies and it is predicted to become an elliptical

Merging Systems:

It has been found that galaxies often merge due to their small separation in comparison with their size. There is a huge cumulative gravitational pull of each galaxy towards the other which causes them to merge.

However, whilst galaxies are merging, stars or star systems (like the Solar System) do not actually collide, as the distances between them are too great. Many stars or star systems may be thrown off into space or their orbits completely changed. This results in most of the stars having complex orbits and moving in random directions, which is one of the reasons merged galaxies become irregular or peculiar eventually becoming elliptical.

In the merging process of two galaxies, large amounts of gas and dust are directed towards the central region, and are compressed. This induces active star formation. Galaxies with high rates of star formation are known as 'starburst' galaxies. The new stars, along with the Active Galactic Nuclei, heat up the surrounding dust which then emits huge amounts of infrared radiation. Such galaxies are known as *(Ultra)-Luminous Infrared Galaxies (U)-LIRGs*

Once the galaxies have fully converged and much of the gas and dust is used up, a redlooking elliptical galaxy is formed and there is very little star formation.

CHAPTER NO 7:

INFALLING HALO MODEL

METHODOLOGY

For the purpose of infalling evolving Halo model we have considered Halo as an isothermal sphere. The Halo is free of any molecular hydrogen because of high intensity Lyman Werner (LW) photons that dissociates molecular hydrogen H_2 . A massive black hole $M_{BH} = 10^4 - 10^6 M_{\odot}$ is present at the centre of proto galactic disc at redshift $z_i \sim 20 - 10$. The dark matter halo is assumed to have a temperature of $T_{vir} = 8000 K$. Under these conditions, there is a strong likelihood that a DCBH hosting halo to undergo merger in its evolution.

The evolving Halo model follow the growth of a proto galactic disc in an isolated growing halo after the formation of Massive black hole seed.

PARAMETERS

Halo Growth

A halo is a large region filled with hot gas that surrounds a galaxy. Every galaxy has a halo, and these regions are crucial to understanding not only how galaxies formed and evolved but also how the universe progressed from a kernel (seed) of helium and hydrogen to a cosmological expanse teeming with stars, planets, comets, and all other sorts of celestial constituents. Yet the exact mass and shape of the halo are not known. Unlike the Galaxy's spiral arms, which contain bright stars, the halo is mostly dark (Tricia Talbert, 2020)

Figure 7-1 Main components of Halo.

According to CDM cosmology, dark matter halos form hierarchically. Smaller halos form first at higher redshift, and then merge along to form larger halos as the time progresses. This picture is a generic consequence of the shape of CDM power spectrum. In the simulated universe, high-redshift small halos that eventually settle their mass into a final halo are referred to as “progenitors” of the halo. With the identified mass and redshift of each progenitor, one can chain up these quantities chronologically and generate the “merging tree” of a dark halo.

Based upon the dark halo merging tree, other essential assumptions, for instance gas cooling, star formation, feedbacks and so on can therefore be deployed to model the formation of galaxies. Although the construction of a merging tree involves several artificial definitions such as halo mass, it is nevertheless an efficient way that enables us to develop a backbone for modelling galaxy formation. (Li, 2010)

Figure 7-2 Left: Schematic representation of dark matter halo merger tree. In a hierarchical model, halo grows by the accretion of smaller neighbouring halos. Right: A simulated Milky Way-size CDM halo. The circles in the main image mark six sub-halos that are sh

In Λ CDM theory on structure formation, it is said that galaxies form and evolve within dark matter halos. By analysing the evolving property of halos, we can better understand the evolution of galaxies. Therefore, understanding the evolution and growth of halos is important factor in understanding the evolution of DCBH and proto galactic disc.

We have considered a system that consists of Dark Matter Halo, Massive Black Hole Seed, and Proto-Galactic Disc. The total mass of a system, M_{tot} , is made up of halo and baryons that forms the black hole and proto galactic disc. Suppose that the total mass increase through the

cosmological accretion of mass onto the system. The following equation is used to calculate the growth of the system (Dekel A., 2013)

$$M_{tot}(z) = M_{tot,i} e^{-\zeta(z-z_i)}$$

$$M_{tot,i} = \text{Total initial mass at } z_i$$

$$\frac{dM_{tot}}{dz} = M_{tot,i} e^{-\zeta(z-z_i)} \frac{d}{dz} [-\zeta(z-z_i)]$$

$$\frac{dM_{tot}}{dz} = -\zeta(1-0) M_{tot,i} e^{-\zeta(z-z_i)}$$

$$\frac{dM_{tot}}{dz} = -\zeta M_{tot}$$

$$\zeta = \text{Halo growth rate parameter}$$

Disc Instability

The local stability of the disc against gravitational collapse is parameterised by Toomre stability parameter. It is a relationship between different parameters which can be used to determine whether the disc is stable against gravitational collapse or not. (Toomre A., 1964). Gravitational instabilities of galactic disc are studied to understand the connection between gravitational instabilities and star formation rate. Both these factors are important for understanding the formation and evolution of discs.

$$Q = \frac{c_s \kappa}{\pi G \Sigma}$$

$c_s = \text{sound speed}$

$\kappa = \text{epicyclic frequency}$

$\Sigma = \text{Total surface density}$

The disc is stable against gravitational collapse if

$$Q_{\text{Toomre}} > 1$$

This disc is unstable to gravitational instabilities if

$$Q_{\text{Toomre}} < 1$$

And partially stable if

$$Q_{\text{Toomre}} \sim 1$$

For a particle in a closed orbit, the *epicyclic frequency is the frequency of radial motions due to a small perturbation in the orbit*. For example, consider a planet orbiting a star in a circular orbit. If the motion of this planet is slightly perturbed in the radial direction, its orbit will change from circular to elliptical. Thus, its distance from the star (the centre of the potential) is no longer constant, but oscillating between a maximum and minimum distance (apoapsis and periapsis).

The epicyclic frequency is the frequency of these oscillations. (Almog Yalinewich, 2017). Thus, the epicyclic frequency measures the differential rotation. It is expressed as (Eastwood, 2019)

$$\kappa = 2\Omega \sqrt{1 + \frac{1}{2} \frac{d \ln \Omega}{d \ln R}}$$

$\Omega = \text{Angular frequency}$

$R = \text{Radial Distance}$

Differential rotation is seen when different parts of rotating object move with different angular velocity (it refers to how fast an object rotate relative to another point, or how fast the orientation of object changes with time.) Galaxies and protostars show differential rotations. The equatorial regions rotate faster than regions close to poles

Inflow Rate

We have considered an infalling halo model in which gas inflow occurs. Gas inflow and outflow are main drivers of galaxy evolution. According to widely accepted cosmological models, the first galaxies began to form 13 or 14 billion years ago. Like living organisms, these galaxies continue to evolve with time, accrete and eject materials with time.

The massive stars in a galaxy ejects out most of its material during supernova. This material then in-falls back into the disc over time (Matt Williams, 2019). However, the detailed properties of gas flows are difficult to measure. For example, a recent study showed that milky way experienced a dormant period about 7 billion years ago, which lasted for 2 billion years. This was because of shock waves that caused the interstellar medium hot enough to stop the inflow of cold gas in our galaxy. Over time, the gas cool again and star formation began to occur (Matt Williams, 2019). That's why we put some constraints on flow rates.

Gravitational energy or gravitational potential energy is the energy a massive object has in relation to another massive object due to gravity. Gravitational energy increases when distance decreases or when matter falls inward.

Since the total angular momentum of disc is conserved, the angular momentum loss of mass falling into the centre (inward) has to be compensated by angular momentum gain of mass far from centre. In other words, mass must be transported outwards from disc.

According to observations, if matter fall inwards (accretion), it must lose not only its gravitational energy but also its angular momentum. We have considered that mass transport in disc is described using some viscosity. (Shakura, 1973)

Proposed an accretion disc model in which the angular momentum is transported outward by action of some kind of viscosity. It is given by

$$v = \alpha_v c_s H$$

$$c_s = \text{Disc sound speed}$$

$$H = \text{Disc scale height} = \frac{c_s}{\Omega}$$

$$\alpha_v = \text{Viscosity parameter}$$

$$v = \alpha_v c_s \left(\frac{c_s}{\Omega} \right)$$

$$v = \alpha_v \frac{c_s^2}{\Omega}$$

The inflow rate of gas as a result of this viscosity is defined as

$$\dot{M} = \frac{v \pi \Sigma_g}{2} \left| \frac{d \ln \Omega}{d \ln R} \right|$$

$$v = \alpha_v \frac{c_s^2}{\Omega}$$

$$\dot{M} = \frac{\alpha_v c_s^2 \pi \Sigma_g}{2 \Omega} \left| \frac{d \ln \Omega}{d \ln R} \right|$$

$$\Sigma_g = \text{Gas surface density}$$

Putting value of Q_{Toomre} and epicyclic frequency, κ

$$\Sigma_g = \frac{c_s \kappa}{\pi G Q}$$

$$\kappa = 2 \Omega \sqrt{1 + \frac{1}{2} \frac{d \ln \Omega}{d \ln R}}$$

$$\dot{M}_{\text{inf}} = \frac{\pi \alpha_v c_s^2}{2 \Omega} \left(\frac{c_s \kappa}{\pi G Q} \right) \left| \frac{d \ln \Omega}{d \ln R} \right|$$

$$\dot{M} = \frac{\alpha_v c_s^3}{2 \Omega G Q} \left| \frac{d \ln \Omega}{d \ln R} \right| \times 2 \Omega \left[1 + \frac{1}{2} \frac{d \ln \Omega}{d \ln R} \right]^{1/2}$$

$$\dot{M}_{\text{inf}} = \frac{\alpha_v c_s^3}{G Q} \left| \frac{d \ln \Omega}{d \ln R} \right| \left[1 + \frac{1}{2} \frac{d \ln \Omega}{d \ln R} \right]^{1/2}$$

$\Omega = \text{Angular frequency}$

$R = \text{Radial Distance}$

$d \ln \Omega / d \ln R = \text{The gradient of angular frequency in terms of logarithmic derivative.}$

For the sake of our model, we have considered that the major contribution comes from the gravitational instability parameter. Based on this assumption, we will have two inflow rates.

Optimistic Inflow Rate: *The inflow rate is maximum when the value of Toomre instability parameter is minimum*

$$Q_{\text{Toomre}} = \text{Minimum}$$

$$Q_{\text{Toomre}} < 1$$

When Toomre instability parameter has minimum contribution with respect to R , the disc is most unstable. Consequently, we will have maximum inflow rate of gas in the disc

Conservative Inflow Rate: The inflow rate is minimum when the value of Toomre instability parameter is maximum. \dot{M} and Q_{Toomre} has inverse relation. Therefore, increasing the value of Q_{Toomre} decreases the gas inflow rate

$$Q_{\text{Toomre}} = \text{Maximum}$$

$$Q_{\text{Toomre}} > \text{or } \sim 1$$

For the sake of simplicity, we have considered that gas inflow rate is minimum when

$$Q_{\text{Toomre}} = 1$$

When Toomre instability parameter has maximum contribution with respect to R , the disc is most stable. We can therefore consider that we will have conservative inflow rate at we will have conservative inflow rate at $R_{c,in}$ and $R_{c,out}$.

$R_{c,in}$ = Inner Critical Radius. It is the innermost radius where star formation can occur. And, star formation can only occur when $Q_{\text{Toomre}} < 1$

$R_{c,out}$ = Outer Critical Radius. It is the maximum radius where star formation can occur.

The **optimistic** and conservative inflow rates are shown below (Eastwood, 2019)

Black hole Growth

A black hole is an astronomical object with a gravitational pull so strong that nothing, not even light, can escape it. Once born, black holes can grow in two ways. They can accrete mass from the space around them or they can merge with each other, forming one more massive black hole. Black holes and their growth play a key role in the evolution of galaxies (Amy Oliver, 2020). Understanding how black holes formed, grew and co-evolved with galaxies is fundamental to our understanding and knowledge of the universe (Cosmos, 2020).

When a black hole grows via accretion, it feeds the nearby gas that is pulled in by the black hole's intense gravity. In the early universe, there was plenty of gas available so, larger black holes grow by accretion. Similarly, smaller black holes in early universe grow by merging with other small black holes. However, the opposite is true for modern universe (Caitlyn Buongiorno, 2020)

Figure 7-3 Small black holes usually grow through accretion and large black holes usually grow through mergers in the modern universe. However, the opposite was true in the early universe (Caitlyn Buongiorno, 2020).

For our model, we have considered that black hole grows through accretion. Star formation process reduces the gas. The star formation depletes the gas reservoir, reducing the rate of accretion of black hole. But the inflow of gas in the reservoir can increase the rate of accretion of black hole.

Suppose that the black hole is fed by the gas from reservoir. The gas reservoir is itself fed by inflow of gas. The rate of increase in mass of the reservoir as well the rate of black hole accretion can be determined by (Eastwood, 2019)

$$\dot{M}_{res} = \dot{M}_{inf} - \dot{M}_{BH}$$

Growth of black hole through accretion as greater potential for providing the necessary increase in mass. However, accretion is still limited by the supply of gas to the black hole as well as the rate at which black hole can accrete.

For gas to be available to the black hole for accretion, it has to reach the gravitational sphere of influence of black hole. Suppose that the reservoir is under the gravitational influence of black hole, because only then black hole can accrete. Therefore, the accretion rate of black hole can be calculated as

$$\dot{M}_{BH} = \min[\dot{M}_{res}, \dot{M}_{Edd}]$$

Eddington luminosity is the maximum luminosity a body can achieve when there is balance between force of radiation acting outward and gravitational force acting inward. When a star exceeds Eddington limit, it will produce very high intensity radiations. For any object, there is maximum luminosity beyond which radiation pressure will overcome gravity, and materials outside the object will be forced away from it rather than falling inward. *The accretion rate for which the black hole radiates at the Eddington luminosity is known as Eddington accretion rate.* For the purpose of the model, we have

$$\dot{M}_{Edd} = \frac{M_{BH}}{t_{sal}}$$

t_{sal} = Salpeter timescale or Salpeter time

It is the timescale for black hole growth or the time a black hole will take to double its mass if accreting at Eddington limit.

However, if no limit is imposed on the growth of the black hole, such as Eddington limit, we can assume that the inflow from disc is directly feeding the black hole. This assumption corresponds to no gas reservoir and

$$\dot{M}_{inf} = \dot{M}_{BH}$$

This is true only when we have not considered any limit on the black hole growth. However, when Eddington limit is considered in the model, the results would be different.

For simplicity, throughout the model we will consider that no limit is applied on the growth of black hole.

CHAPTER 08:

RESULTS OF MODEL

Black Hole Seed Masses

In the vast garden of the universe, the heaviest black holes grew from seeds. Nourished by the gas and dust they consumed, or by merging with other dense objects, these seeds grew in size and heft to form the centres of galaxies (Elizabeth Landau, 2019). There are many hypotheses that describes the formation of the seed masses.. We have studied the growth history of black hole with two different seed masses

— $M_{seed} = 100 M_{\odot}$
 — $M_{seed} = 10^6 M_{\odot}$

We have considered that no limit is imposed on the growth of black hole.

The line indicates the time at which disc becomes unstable or when $Q_{Toomre} < 1$. Before this time, the black hole seed masses do not grow because of disc stability.

Conservative inflow rate or inflow rate when $Q_{Toomre} \sim 1$. The conservative inflow rate occurs at critical radii.

Graph 4

The lower black hole seed shows a sudden increase in its mass. This is because no limit is considered on the growth of black hole

For lower black hole seed masses, the disc becomes unstable earlier as compared to higher black hole

Similarly, conservative inflow rate for lower seed mass

Star Formation

Star formation occurs when the disc is unstable to gravitational instabilities. With the passage of time, the star formation rate increases throughout the unstable region. Star formation in the disc reduces the growth of black hole. This happens because the gas that otherwise contribute in the accretion of black hole is now utilized in the star formation process. Star formation and black hole growth are both fed from the gas content of the disc and they are therefore in competition over the same gas supply (Eastwood, 2019). Following results shows how the black hole growth is affected during star formation and no star formation process.

Graph 5

The optimistic inflow rate when the star formation occurs. It is less than the case where there is no star formation. When the star formation occurs, the final mass of black hole is less because the gas that is used in the growth of black hole is now utilized in star formation

Conservative inflow rate of gas when there is no star formation. It occurs at critical radii where $Q_{Toomre} \sim 1$. At this stage the disc is partially unstable

Viscosity

The mass transport in disc is described using some viscosity. If we consider the optimistic inflow rate, then the final black hole mass is 10^7 . This mass of seed black hole is much smaller for the formation of supermassive black hole. From the mass inflow equation

$$\dot{M}_{inf} = \frac{\pi\alpha_v c_s^2}{2\Omega} \left(\frac{c_s \kappa}{\pi G Q} \right) \left| \frac{d \ln \Omega}{d \ln R} \right|$$

Increasing the viscosity parameter will increase the inflow of gas which correspondingly increase the black hole growth. The greater the viscosity parameter, the greater will be inflow rate and hence, the black hole can accrete more rapidly and therefore can reach to higher black hole mass. The final black hole mass changes with different initial seed masses. This can be observed from following result

Halo growth rate

The growth rate of the halo determines the rate at which the disc can grow. Increasing the halo growth rate parameter will increase the accretion rate onto the disc (Eastwood, 2019). This will increase the disc mass and the disc becomes more unstable. This leads to increase in the inflow rate in the disc. Increasing mass of black hole increases the stability of disc, while increasing the disc mass decreases the stability of disc (Eastwood D. S., 2018)

At lower halo growth rate parameter, the disc mass does not grow rapidly. For lower halo growth rate parameter, the disc mass does not grow significantly and the disc is stable for more time. However, this

is opposite for higher growth rate parameter. For higher growth rate parameter, the disc mass grows more rapidly resulting in a higher inflow rate. A higher inflow rate will result in a higher growth rate of black hole. (Eastwood, 2019). Increasing the growth rate of the halo will increase the disc mass at a given time.

ANALYSIS OF HALO MODEL:

For the parameters discussed here for the infalling halo model, there is no such case where the growth of black hole mass reaches $10^9 M_\odot$ at 1 Gyr (nearer redshift ~ 6) as discussed in (Mortlock, 2011). Observational studies have suggested that if we neglect all the feedback effects and star formation and consider no limit on the growth of black hole than black hole can grow up to $10^9 M_\odot$. However, this is not possible as the halo becomes overly massive $\sim 10^{16} M_\odot$, while halo with mass of $\sim 10^{13} M_\odot$ should exist in the universe at 1 Gyr.

DCBH are likely to form in the neighbors of massive galaxies. With the passage of time, the DCBH will undergo a merger with a neighboring halo. This merger will greatly impact the evolution of black hole. A black hole can grow more rapidly during mergers of DCBH host halo with central galaxy.

In this model, we have investigated the growth of massive seed black holes through the inflow of gas from proto galactic discs. The inflow rate of gas is (Eastwood, 2019)

$$\dot{M}_{inf} = \frac{\pi \alpha_v c_s^2}{2\Omega} \left(\frac{c_s \kappa}{\pi G Q} \right) \left| \frac{d \ln \Omega}{d \ln R} \right|$$

It is the function of stability parameter and therefore it depends on both the mass of disc and mass of halo. We find that increasing the halo growth parameter will increase the inflow of gas in the disc (*Graph 07*). Thus, supermassive black holes can grow more rapidly in faster growing halos.

Star formation also plays a key role in the growth of halo (*Graph 06*). If we consider the star formation, then some of the gas which otherwise contributes to the growth of black hole will be utilized in forming stars. This will reduce the black hole growth.

Moreover, we have considered an isothermal case. This is because the inflow rate is

$$\dot{M}_{inf} \propto c_s^2$$

Any change in temperature would change the sound speed which will affect the inflow rate of gas.

From these results, we have concluded that supermassive black holes with masses $\sim 10^9 M_\odot$ can not be formed only because of viscosity driven inflows and hence only the viscosity driven inflow is insufficient to feed the massive seed black holes. There must be other contributors. This can be resolved by considering the effects of torque exerted on the galactic disc from gravitational instabilities in the disc. (Hopkins, 2011) found that the inflow rates calculated using the gravitational torque matched the simulations more closely. Calculating the inflow rate using the gravitational torque would increase the inflow rate that correspondingly increases the accretion of the black hole.

CHAPTER 9

ALADIN: OBESERVING MERGERS

Introduction to Aladin:

Aladin is an interactive software sky atlas allowing the user to visualize digitized astronomical images superimpose entries from astronomical catalogues or database.

Most of available image and catalogue over the internet are available and notably SIMBAD, NED, Vizier, MAST/STScI, CADM, HEASARC, SLOAN, NVSS...

Aladin is dedicated to professional astronomers. It can be also used by teachers or undergraduate students or amateur astronomers. It is free under Uds/CNRS licence. It has been translated in English, Italian, German, Persian, Russian, Chinese...

Aladin is mainly used for;

- Visualising and checking catalogues and images
- Searching and browsing available astronomical data
- Preparing observations
- Creating field charts

The Aladin software can be used directly in a Web page for dynamically visualising astronomical data into a simple navigator such as Internet Explorer or Firefox. Many institutes are using this way for providing their own data to their users (NED, CADM, MAST, ESAC, ESO..)

Aladin is developed by the centre de Donnees astronomiques de Strasbourg (CDS). It is compatible with most computer configurations including Windows, Linux and Mac. It does not require significant resources unless it has to handle very large catalogues (several hundreds of thousands of objects)

Created in 1999, Aladin is supporting emerging standards of the Virtual Observatory. It is compliant with other visualization and analysis tools (IDL, VOPlot, TOPCAT, Specview, Splat, VOSpec ...). All these key topics allow Aladin to be a powerful data exploration and integration tool as well as a science enabler.

Fig 9.1 Aladin software

Observations with XMM Newton:

XMM – Newton is the biggest scientific satellite ever built in Europe, its telescope mirrors are amongst the most powerful ever developed in the world, and it has extremely sensitive cameras suitable for imaging and spectroscopy. The satellite launched in 1999 and is still in operation today.

There are two types of instruments aboard XMM-Newton, which takes X-ray, ultraviolet and optical images

The European Imaging Camera (EPIC). It is composed of three detectors and takes X-ray images of even very weak X-ray signals. Therefore it is a useful device for investigating objects extremely far away

The Reflection Grating Spectrometer (RGS) obtains spectra from the incoming X-ray radiation to study the physical conditions of the particular source being observed

Optical Monitor (OM) which is an optical/ultraviolet telescope. It looks at the same sources as the X-ray instruments simultaneously to help scientists by providing additional data about a source

Fig 9.2 Artistic impression of XMM Newton Telescope.

Credits: ESA

USING THE ARCHIVES TO OBSERVE AND EXPLORE NGC 6240:

TOOLS:

XMM-Newton Science Archive (XSA): This archive provides simple and flexible access to data from the XMM-Newton mission. XSA can be opened from here: <http://archives.esac.esa.int/xsa>

Aladin: This is an interactive program providing access to sky atlases which can be used to visualize astronomical images.

STEP 1:

Search the location NGC 6240

Location of NGC 6240 sky

STEP 2: Open XMM archives.

Single Object Search
Multi-Object Search

Search
Clear

Name
 Equatorial
 Galactic

Target in Field Of View Circle Box

Search the galaxy NGC 6240

Resolve Given by Proposer

► Filters for Observation, Proposal and Catalogue Searches

▼ Display options

Observations	PPS Sources	Slew Observations	Catalogues/Upper Limits
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pointed Observations <input type="checkbox"/> Exposures <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> EPIC Exposures <input type="checkbox"/> OM Exposures <input type="checkbox"/> RGS Exposures <input type="checkbox"/> Proposals <input type="checkbox"/> Publications	<input type="checkbox"/> EPIC PPS Sources <input type="checkbox"/> OM PPS Sources <input type="checkbox"/> Slew PPS Sources	<input type="checkbox"/> Slew Observations <input type="checkbox"/> Slew Obs. Segments <input type="checkbox"/> Slew Publications	<input type="checkbox"/> 4XMM-DR10 Filtered Catalogue <input type="checkbox"/> 4XMM-DR10s Filtered Stack Cat <input type="checkbox"/> OM Source Catalogue <input type="checkbox"/> Slew Survey Clean Catalogue <div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 2px; margin-top: 5px;"> <input type="checkbox"/> Upper Limits </div>

Single Object Search
Multi-Object Search

Search
Clear

Name
 Equatorial
 Galactic

Target in Field Of View Circle Box

Resolve Given by Proposer

► Filters for Observation, Proposal and Catalogue Searches

▼ Display options

Observations	PPS Sources	Slew Observations	Catalogues/Upper Limits
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pointed Observations <input type="checkbox"/> Exposures <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> EPIC Exposures <input type="checkbox"/> OM Exposures <input type="checkbox"/> RGS Exposures <input type="checkbox"/> Proposals <input type="checkbox"/> Publications	<input type="checkbox"/> EPIC PPS Sources <input type="checkbox"/> OM PPS Sources <input type="checkbox"/> Slew PPS Sources	<input type="checkbox"/> Slew Observations <input type="checkbox"/> Slew Obs. Segments <input type="checkbox"/> Slew Publications	<input type="checkbox"/> 4XMM-DR10 Filtered Catalogue <input type="checkbox"/> 4XMM-DR10s Filtered Stack Cat <input type="checkbox"/> OM Source Catalogue <input type="checkbox"/> Slew Survey Clean Catalogue <div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 2px; margin-top: 5px;"> <input type="checkbox"/> Upper Limits </div>

Select All

This will load the Observation IDs and the corresponding data, presented in tabular format. For NGC 6240 there should be 8 in total.

XMM-Newton Science Archive

HOME SEARCH COMMAND & URL ACCESS INTERACTIVE ANALYSIS TAP QUERIES ASTROQUERY

Back to Search Close all

Results #1

OBSERVATIONS (7)

Columns Column units Display selected Add to Basket Save table as Send table to Reprocess RGS Spectra

	Obs.ID	EPIC	RGS	BKGD	ESASky	Target	RA	DEC	Rev	Distance	Start Date	End Date	Dur.	
<input type="checkbox"/>	0147420201					NGC 6240	16h 52m 58.90s	+02d 24' 03.0"	597	0.01	2003-03-14 18:06:14	2003-03-15 05:45:24	41950	IR GAL
<input type="checkbox"/>	0147420301					NGC 6240	16h 52m 58.90s	+02d 24' 03.0"	599	0.01	2003-03-18 21:01:56	2003-03-19 04:49:53	28077	IR GAL
<input type="checkbox"/>	0147420401					NGC 6240	16h 52m 58.90s	+02d 24' 03.0"	673	0.01	2003-08-13 10:29:32	2003-08-13 14:24:47	14115	IR GAL
<input type="checkbox"/>	0147420501					NGC 6240	16h 52m 58.90s	+02d 24' 03.0"	677	0.01	2003-08-21 10:25:09	2003-08-21 19:05:28	31219	IR GAL
<input type="checkbox"/>	0147420601					NGC 6240	16h 52m 58.90s	+02d 24' 03.0"	681	0.01	2003-08-29 11:25:15	2003-08-29 13:58:49	8214	IR GAL
<input type="checkbox"/>	0101640101			N/A		NGC 6240	16h 52m 58.58s	+02d 24' 04.0"	144	0.07	2000-09-22 01:38:46	2000-09-22 10:00:37	30111	IR GAL
<input type="checkbox"/>	0101640601					NGC 6240	16h 52m 58.58s	+02d 24' 04.0"	413	0.07	2002-03-12 21:37:24	2002-03-13 02:51:55	18871	IR GAL

1 of 1 Page size: 100 Displaying 1-7 of 7

Results #1 Results #2

OBSERVATIONS (7)

Columns Column units Display selected Add to Basket Save table as Send table to Reprocess RGS Spectra

Column selection

- Obs.ID
- EPIC
- MT EPIC
- RGS
- RGS
- RGS
- MT RGS
- BKGD
- V

Select All Clear OK

	Obs.ID	EPIC	RGS	BKGD	ESASky	Target	RA	DEC	Rev	Distance	Start Date	End Date	Dur.	
<input type="checkbox"/>	0147420201					NGC 6240	16h 52m 58.90s	+02d 24' 03.0"	597	0.01	2003-03-14 18:06:14	2003-03-15 05:45:24	41950	IR GAL
<input type="checkbox"/>	0147420301					NGC 6240	16h 52m 58.90s	+02d 24' 03.0"	599	0.01	2003-03-18 21:01:56	2003-03-19 04:49:53	28077	IR GAL
<input type="checkbox"/>	0147420401					NGC 6240	16h 52m 58.90s	+02d 24' 03.0"	673	0.01	2003-08-13 10:29:32	2003-08-13 14:24:47	14115	IR GAL
<input type="checkbox"/>	0147420501					NGC 6240	16h 52m 58.90s	+02d 24' 03.0"	677	0.01	2003-08-21 10:25:09	2003-08-21 19:05:28	31219	IR GAL
<input type="checkbox"/>	0147420601					NGC 6240	16h 52m 58.90s	+02d 24' 03.0"	681	0.01	2003-08-29 11:25:15	2003-08-29 13:58:49	8214	IR GAL
<input type="checkbox"/>	0101640101			N/A		NGC 6240	16h 52m 58.58s	+02d 24' 04.0"	144	0.07	2000-09-22 01:38:46	2000-09-22 10:00:37	30111	IR GAL
<input type="checkbox"/>	0101640601					NGC 6240	16h 52m 58.58s	+02d 24' 04.0"	413	0.07	2002-03-12 21:37:24	2002-03-13 02:51:55	18871	IR GAL

1 of 1 Page size: 100 Displaying 1-7 of 7

Column selection

- Obs.ID
- EPIC
- RGS
- Target
- RA
- Dec
- PA
- Rev
- Distance

Select All Clear OK

Select these options

Selected Columns Are Shown Here

Obs.ID	EPIC	RGS	Target	RA	DEC	PA	Rev	Distance
0147420201			NGC 6240	16h 52m 58.90s	+02d 24' 03.0"	92.3	597	0.01
0147420301			NGC 6240	16h 52m 58.90s	+02d 24' 03.0"	90.5	599	0.01
0147420401			NGC 6240	16h 52m 58.90s	+02d 24' 03.0"	286.8	673	0.01
0147420501			NGC 6240	16h 52m 58.90s	+02d 24' 03.0"	283.3	677	0.01
0147420601			NGC 6240	16h 52m 58.90s	+02d 24' 03.0"	280	681	0.01
0101640601		N/A	NGC 6240	16h 52m 58.58s	+02d 24' 04.0"	271.3	144	0.07
0101640601			NGC 6240	16h 52m 58.58s	+02d 24' 04.0"	92.8	413	0.07

OPEN THE EPIC IMAGE OF 0101640601

Send this image to Aladin

EPIC image for galaxy NGC 6240.

Any kind of data or images will be uploaded here.

STEP 03

OBSERVATIONS (7) ✕

Columns Column units Display selected Add to Basket Save table as Send table to Reprocess RGS Spectra

			Obs.ID	EPIC	RGS	Target	RA	DEC	PA	Rev	Distance
<input type="checkbox"/>			0147420201			NGC 6240	16h 52m 58.90s	+02d 24' 03.0"	92.3	597	0.01
<input type="checkbox"/>			0147420301			NGC 6240	16h 52m 58.90s	+02d 24' 03.0"	90.5	599	0.01
<input type="checkbox"/>			0147420401			NGC 6240	16h 52m 58.90s	+02d 24' 03.0"	286.8	673	0.01
<input type="checkbox"/>			0147420501			NGC 6240	16h 52m 58.90s	+02d 24' 03.0"	283.3	677	0.01
<input type="checkbox"/>			0147420601			NGC 6240	16h 52m 58.90s	+02d 24' 03.0"	280	681	0.01
<input type="checkbox"/>			0101640101			NGC 6240	16h 52m 58.58s	+02d 24' 04.0"	271.3	144	0.07
<input type="checkbox"/>			0101640601			NGC 6240	16h 52m 58.58s	+02d 24' 04.0"	92.8	413	0.07

Click on this obs.ID to open a new result ta

Click on EPIC PPS SOURCES

OBSERVATIONS (1) ✕ EXPOSURES (16) ✕ EPIC PPS SOURCES (49) ✕ OM PPS SOURCES (49) ✕ 4XMM-DR10 CAT (49) ✕ OM SOURCE CAT (48) ✕ PUBLICATIONS (37) ✕ PROPOSALS (1) ✕

Columns Column units Display selected Add to Basket Save table as Send table to Reprocess RGS Spectra

		Obs.ID	EPIC	RGS	BKGD	ESASky	Target	RA	DEC	Rev	Start Date	End Date	Dur.	Target Type
<input type="checkbox"/>		0101640601					NGC 6240	16h 52m 58.58s	+02d 24' 04.0"	413	2002-03-12 21:37:24	2002-03-13 02:51:55	18871	IR GALAXY RADIO QUIE

1 of 1 Page size: 100 Displaying 1-1 of 1

Send this table to Aladin

Results #1 ✕ Results #2 ✕ Results #3 ✕ Results #4 ✕

OBSERVATIONS (1) ✕ EXPOSURES (16) ✕ EPIC PPS SOURCES (49) ✕ OM PPS SOURCES (49) ✕ 4XMM-DR10 CAT (49) ✕ OM SOURCE CAT (48) ✕ PUBLICATIONS (37) ✕ PROPOSALS (1) ✕

Columns Column units Display selected Add to Basket Save table as Send table to Source Reproc.

		Dwld.	ObsID	Src Nu	RA	DEC	Pos.Err	Det ML	Img	FC	LC	Spec	ESASky	Total Flux	Tot.Flux.Err	Tot Count Rate	Tot
<input type="checkbox"/>			0101640601	1	16h 52m 58.92s	+02d 24' 03.1"	0.1	22160						2.82E-12	5.72E-14	1.0263	
<input type="checkbox"/>			0101640601	2	16h 53m 13.26s	+02d 16' 45.2"	0.5	616						9.07E-14	1.41E-14	0.0843	
<input type="checkbox"/>			0101640601	3	16h 52m 38.06s	+02d 22' 01.4"	0.9	152						9.75E-14	2.69E-14	0.0330	
<input type="checkbox"/>			0101640601	4	16h 53m 31.99s	+02d 35' 18.9"	0.8	153						3.08E-13	8.69E-14	0.0252	
<input type="checkbox"/>			0101640601	5	16h 53m 23.70s	+02d 26' 23.1"	0.9	126						8.68E-14	1.82E-14	0.0301	
<input type="checkbox"/>			0101640601	6	16h 53m 16.44s	+02d 16' 08.0"	0.8	150						3.48E-14	7.57E-15	0.0346	
<input type="checkbox"/>			0101640601	7	16h 53m 44.31s	+02d 25' 18.5"	0.9	138						5.46E-14	1.29E-14	0.0372	
<input type="checkbox"/>			0101640601	8	16h 53m 06.30s	+02d 34' 16.0"	0.8	116						1.19E-13	3.01E-14	0.0382	

1 of 1 Page size: 100 Displaying 1-49 of 49

Each circle is an X-ray source, like stars and galaxies, within the image

STEP 04:

To load the last data image:

- Go to the FILE
- Open SERVER SELECTOR
- The " *server selector*" window lets you know and query the different astronomical databases that can be accessed with Aladin.
- Clicking on server selector will open a new tab.

Another version of NGC 6240 using sky view who locates the high energy astronomical objects present in the galaxy such as SMBHs. Red dot identifies the presence of such objects.

STEP 05:

- Again choose the XSA image and check the box to open its image in the window.

Check this box

Click on this to choose pixels

Observational data about supermassive objects at center

a different pixel color indicates the presence of three supermassive source

STEP 06:

- Now we will use the contour feature. it is like a geographical map. The contours show the regions with increased pixel counts, much like in a geographical map where the contours show increase from ground height.

CHAPTER 10:

CONCLUSION

The recent discovery of an 800 million solar mass black hole at a redshift corresponding to 690 million years after the Big Bang is the latest in a growing list of observations of super-massive black holes (SMBHs) that were most likely seeded with masses larger than those expected from the remnants of the first generation of stars.

This thesis investigates the relation of massive black holes on galaxy evolution through a combination of cosmological Models. Firstly, we studied the creation of SMBHs through Direct collapse mechanism (DCBH) and factors affecting it. We found out that the creation of these seeds require some specific conditions such as LW radiations, gas temperature at 8000K, conservation of Angular momentum. This thesis predicts the formation of these seeds in dark matter haloes in isothermal sphere which prevents fragmentation and causes the gas to collapse under its own gravity forming seed black holes.

Secondly, we studied the growth of gravitational instabilities in an isolated protogalaxy disc as it progresses into a fully-formed galaxy in the presence of a massive seed black hole formed directly through isothermal collapse. The model shows for the first time how the gravitational effects of a seed black hole lead to an increase in the stability of the disc and an increase in the star formation timescale in the region of the disc close to the black hole. This gravitational imprint of the black hole on the galactic disc has the effect of suppressing star formation. We studied the graphs of the disc galaxy model from the epoch of seed formation to understand how star formation in seed hosting galaxies is further regulated by a combination of gravitational stability and the accretion of gas onto the black hole.

We also studied how the growth of massive seed black holes is regulated by the mass and momentum transport in the disc. The inward accretion of gas towards the central massive black hole and therefore the accretion of gas onto the black hole itself is a function of the stability of the disc. The stabilising effect of the black hole therefore has the potential to regulate the inflow of gas, depending on the relative masses of the galaxy disc and black hole.

We find that even in the regime where the inflow rate is not affected by the presence of the black hole, viscosity driven accretion is too inefficient for even massive seeds to grow into a SMBHs. This indicates the isolated growth of SMBHs is not possible. Indeed, merger events or other processes which are efficient at dissipating angular momentum are required to provide the necessary rapid accretion of gas for SMBHs to form.

We also investigated the merger interaction using a merger remnant NGC 6240 through simulations. We observed the core of NGC 6240 which shows three black holes present in the galaxy which indicates that these will merge to form a super massive black hole after some time. The hypothetical mass of this super massive black hole support the hypothesis that merger interaction plays a role in the evolution of these SMBHs.

GLOSARRY

Astronomy: *It is a branch of physics that is concerned with celestial objects. It is the study of everything in the universe including objects which we can see with our naked eyes or not. It includes stars, planets, nebula, meteors, comets, galaxies and various phenomena related with these objects.*

Accretion: *It is the increase in mass of any celestial object due to its gravitational attraction. Almost all astronomical objects evolve through accretion process.*

Accretion disc: *It is a disc of gas that revolves around the central object such as black hole.*

Black hole: *It is a region in space with highly condensed matter, where the gravity is so strong that nothing, not even the light, can escape from it. Black holes cannot be seen directly.*

Galaxy: *A galaxy is a massive collection of gas, dust, millions of stars and black holes. A galaxy consists of a supermassive black hole at its centre.*

Light year: *A light year is a distance which a light can travel in one year. It is a unit of distance that is used to measure astronomical distances. In one year, light can travel about 5.88 trillion miles.*

Luminosity: *It is the total amount of electromagnetic radiations emitted by an object per unit time by an astronomical object.*

Parsec: *It is a unit of distance used in astronomy. It is approximately equal to 3.26 light years.*

Proto galaxy: *It can be defined as 'pre-galaxy'. It is the accumulation of gas and dust that is forming into a galaxy as a result of gravitational attraction.*

Redshift: *It is a key concept that is used to determine how an object in space is moving compared to us. The redshift of an object is measured by comparing its spectrum with a reference laboratory spectrum. It is used to measure how the universe is expanding. The higher the redshift, the far the object is from us.*

REFERENCES:

- Agarwal B., et al., 2012, MNRAS, 425, 2854
- Agarwal B., et al., 2014, MNRAS, 443, 648
- Agarwal B., et al., 2016a, MNRAS, 459, 4209
- Agarwal B., et al., 2016b, MNRAS, 460, 4003
- Agarwal B., et al., 2018, preprint, p. arXiv: 1808.09981 (arXiv: 1808.09981)
- Astronomy and Astrophysics, 51, 105
- Bromm V., Loeb A., 2003, ApJ, 596, 34
- Bromm V., Coppi P. S., Larson R. B., 1999, ApJ, 527,L5
- Bromm V., et al., 2009, Nature, 459, 49
- arilli C. L., Walter F., 2013, Annual Review of Astronomy and Astrophysics, 51, 105
- Ceverino D., Dekel A., Bournaud F., 2010, MNRAS, 404, 2151
- Chabrier G., 2003, Publications of the Astronomical Society of the Pacific, 115, 76
- Chandrasekhar S., 1943, ApJ, 97, 255
- Chon S., et al., 2016, ApJ, 832, 134
- Clark P. C., Glover S. C. O., Klessen R. S., 2008, ApJ, 672, 757
- Condon J. J., et al., 2017, ApJ, 834, 184
- Correa C. A., Schaye J., Trayford J. W., 2019, MNRAS, 484, 4401
- Ceverino D., Dekel A., Bournaud F., 2010, MNRAS, 404, 2151
- Chabrier G., 2003, Publications of the Astronomical Society of the Pacific, 115, 763
- Chandrasekhar S., 1943, ApJ, 97, 255
- Chon S., et al., 2016, ApJ, 832, 134
- Clark P. C., Glover S. C. O., Klessen R. S., 2008, ApJ, 672, 757
- Condon J. J., et al., 2017, ApJ, 834, 184
- Correa C. A., Schaye J., Trayford J. W., 2019, MNRAS, 484, 4401
- D’Onghia E., et al., 2006, MNRAS, 372, 1525
- Davé R., et al., 2019, MNRAS, 486, 2827
- De Loore C. W. H., Doom C., 1992, Structure and evolution of single and binary stars. Vol. 179, Springer, Dordrecht, doi:10.1007/978-94-011-2502-4
- De Lucia G., et al., 2012, MNRAS, 423, 1277
- De Rosa G., et al., 2014, ApJ, 790, 145
- Dekel A., Sari R., Ceverino D., 2009, ApJ, 703, 785
- Dekel A., et al., 2013, MNRAS, 435, 999
- Del Moro A., et al., 2016, MNRAS, 456, 2105
- Delvecchio I., et al., 2015, MNRAS, 449, 373
- Devecchi B., Volonteri M., 2009, ApJ, 694, 302
- Devecchi B., et al., 2010, MNRAS, 409, 1057 152
- Di Matteo T., Springel V., Hernquist L., 2005, Nature, 433, 604
- Di Matteo T., et al., 2008, ApJ, 676, 33
- Dib S., Bell E., Burkert A., 2006, ApJ, 638, 797
- Dijkstra M., et al., 2008, MNRAS, 391, 1961
- Dopita M. A., Sutherland R. S., 1996, ApJS, 102, 161
- Dubois Y., et al., 2015, MNRAS, 452, 1502

- Eastwood D. S., Khochfar S., 2018, MNRAS, 480, 5673
- Eastwood D. S., Khochfar S., Trew A., 2019, MNRAS, 488, 2006
- Eastwood D. S., Khochfar S., 2018, MNRAS, 480, 5673
- Eastwood D. S., Khochfar S., Trew A., 2019, MNRAS, 488, 2006
- Edgar R., 2004, *New A Rev.*, 48, 843
- Eisenstein D. J., Loeb A., 1995, *Astrophys. J.*, 443, 11
- Elmegreen B. G., Burkert A., 2010, *ApJ*, 712, 294
- Elmegreen D. M., et al., 2005, *ApJ*, 631, 85
- Elmegreen D. M., et al., 2007, *ApJ*, 658, 763
- Edgar R., 2004, *New A Rev.*, 48, 843
- Fabian A. C., 2012, *ARA&A*, 50, 455
- Fall S. M., Efsthathiou G., 1980, MNRAS, 193, 189
- Fan X., et al., 2003, *AJ*, 125, 1649
- Fan X., et al., 2006, *AJ*, 132, 117
- Fanidakis N., et al., 2012, MNRAS, 419, 2797
- Ferrarese L., Merritt D., 2000, *ApJ*, 539, L9
- Gabor J. M., et al., 2010, MNRAS, 407, 749
- Gebhardt K., et al., 2000, *ApJ*, 539, L13
- Genel S., et al., 2008, *ApJ*, 688, 789
- Glebbeeck E., et al., 2009, *Astron. Astrophys.*, 497, 255
- Governato F., Colpi M., Maraschi L., 1994, MNRAS, 271
- Greif T. H., et al., 2008, MNRAS, 387, 1021
- Greif T. H., et al., 2010, *ApJ*, 716, 510
- Gurzadian V. G., Ozernoi L. M., 1979, *Nature*, 280, 21
- Haring N., Rix H.-W., 2004, *ApJ*, 604, L8
- Hosokawa T., et al., 2013, *ApJ*, 778, 178
- Hoyle F., Lyttleton R. A., 1941, MNRAS, 101, 227
- Kennicutt R. C., Evans N. J., 2012, *ARA&A*, 50, 531
- Khochfar S., Silk J., 2011, MNRAS, 410, L42
- Latif M. A., et al., 2013, MNRAS, 436, 2989
- Latif M. A., et al., 2014, MNRAS, 443, 1979
- Latif M. A., et al., 2016, *ApJ*, 823, 40
- Toomre A., 1964, *ApJ*, 139, 1217
- arilli C. L., Walter F., 2013, *Annual Review of*